

Oxidation of Hydrazine by Some Mono- and Di-Deelectronators.

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Manuscript received 6 February 1973; revised 22 August 1973; accepted 20 September 1973

Oxidation of hydrazine with Ce(IV), $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, periodate and Mo(VI) has been studied potentiometrically. While the first two act as one electron oxidants under all conditions, the periodate behaves as a pure two electron oxidant when taken in excess; in the reverse case, the reaction proceeds through simultaneous one and two electron transfer processes. With Mo(VI) the reaction proceeds predominantly through one electron transfer process. The formation of intermediate polyhydronitrogens seems to be a criterion for mono-deelectronation in these reactions,

IN Kirk and Browne's classification, with respect to oxidation of hydrazine, Ce(IV) and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ have been described as "mono-deelectronators", while Mo(VI) and iodate as "di-deelectronators". There is no mention about periodate. Ce(IV) is reported^{2,3} to oxidise hydrazine quantitatively to N_2 and NH_3 in acid solutions, but no reaction with ferricyanide⁴ occurs in acidic media. Browne and Shetterley⁵ found nitrogen to be the sole product of oxidation of hydrazine by Mo(VI). However, several other workers⁶⁻⁹ have

order of addition of the reagents. The mono-deelectronators Ce(IV), $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ are found to oxidise hydrazine through intermediate polyhydronitrogens, while with di-deelectronators the reaction occurs without such intermediates.

When Ce(IV) solution is added to hydrazine in (Table 1) low acid concentrations (0.5N H_2SO_4) there is a single inflexion corresponding to the stoichiometry:

TABLE 1—CE (IV) SOLUTION WAS GRADUALLY ADDED TO 10 ML. OF HYDRAZINE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Conc. of H_2SO_4 (approx.)	Conc. of Hydrazine	Conc. of Ce(IV) solution	Temp./period of storage	Points of inflex.	Molar ratio Ce(IV)/ N_2H_4
1.	0.5 N	0.004655 M	0.023175 M	30°/24 hr.	2.0	1.0
2.	1 N	0.00931 M	0.0927 M	"	1.0, 2.5	1.0, 2.5
3.	2 N	0.00931 M	0.0927 M	"	1.0, 2.5	1.0, 2.5
4.	3 N	0.00931 M	0.0927 M	"	1.0, 2.5	1.0, 2.5

shown Mo(VI) as a mono-deelectronator. In earlier communications¹⁰⁻¹² we have shown through potentiometric investigations that oxidants like vanadate, dichromate and permanganate react through both mono- and di-deelectronation simultaneously and that the behaviour is much dependent on acid concentrations and the order of addition of the reagents. In the present paper we report the nature of the above mentioned oxidants with regard to "deelectronations" and some other aspects of the mechanism.

Experimental :

Hydrazine sulphate (B.D.H.) solutions were standardised by the iodate¹³ method. Ferricyanide, ceric sulphate and potassium periodate were all Analar grade, while sodium molybdate was Baker analysed sample (U.S.A.) solutions of which were standardised by Jones' reductor method¹⁴.

Details of potentiometric investigations were same as reported earlier¹⁰.

Results and Discussion :

In all these investigations, like earlier ones¹⁰⁻¹², it is found that the nature of oxidation steps and end products are determined largely by the medium and the

At higher concentration of the acid, two inflexions at 1.0 and 2.5 moles Ce(IV) per mole of hydrazine are observed. Since the mixture did not give any test of NH_3 (NH_4^+) it is consistent with the following two step oxidation of hydrazine :

In the reverse case (Table 2) also, at high H_2SO_4 concentration (>4N), the oxidation involves two steps but with different products :

TABLE 2—0.0931 M HYDRAZINE SOLUTION WAS ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00927 M CE(IV) SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Conc. of H_2SO_4 (approx.)	Colour	Temp./period of storage	Points of inflexion	Molar ratio (N_2H_4)/Ce(IV)
1.	0.5 N	Yellow to colourless	30°/24 hr.	1.0	1.0
2.	1 N	"	"	0.5	0.5
3.	2 N	"	"	0.5	0.5
4.	3 N	"	"	0.5	0.5
5.	4 N	"	"	0.5	0.5
6.	6 N	"	"	1.0, 1.5	1.0, 1.5
7.	8 N	"	"	1.0, 1.5	1.0, 1.5

Two inflexions at 1.0 and 1.5 moles of hydrazine per mole of Ce(IV) are correspondingly noticed. In the lower concentration of H₂SO₄ (<N) the inflexion occurs at 1.0 mole and, between N and 4N H₂SO₄, at 0.5 mole :

In case of ferricyanide, when it is added to hydrazine (Table 3) in strongly alkaline media (1N to 4N KOH) a single inflexion at 0.5 mole of the former per mole of the latter is observed. With decrease in alkalinity multiple inflexions are noticed in the curves, the positions of which change with change in pH. For example, at pH=9.018 inflexions are noticed at 0.5, 0.75, 1.25 and 2.5 moles of ferricyanide while at pH≈5, there are at 0.4, 1.4, 1.9 and 2.3 moles of ferricyanide. Assuming that ferricyanide is always reduced to ferrocyanide, and that in strongly alkaline medium, hydrazine is known to be affected by oxygen with H₂O₂ formation^{15,16}, these results can be explained in terms of the following equations :

TABLE 3—0.0932 M FERRICYANIDE SOLUTION WAS ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00937 M HYDRAZINE SULPHATE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Conc. of KOH soln. (approx.)	Colour	Temp./period of storage	Moles of ferricyanide per mole of hydrazine
1.	2 N	Colourless	30°/7 days	0.5
2.	1 N	"	30°/7 days	0.5
3.	1 N	"	90° for one hr./7 days	0.5
4.	0.05 N	"	30°/7 days	0.5
5.	Borate Buffer pH=9.018	Yellow	30°/7 days	0.5, 0.75, 1.25, 2.5
6.	—do—	"	90° for two hr./7 days	0.75, 1.25
7.	aq. medium (pH≈5)	Dark green	30°/7 days	0.4, 1.4, 1.9, 2.3

the two oxidation steps proceeding simultaneously to produce a single inflexion, being covered under the same equilibrium constant. The hydrazyl radical can be stabilised by dimerisation to tetrazane.

At pH 9.018, the results are explained in terms of the following sequence :

On heating the reaction mixture at 90°C for 2 hr. two of these inflexions disappear indicating that the intermediates being less stable at high temperature are oxidised to simpler products.

At pH≈5, the change in stoichiometry is due to the following sequence :

In the reverse case (Table 4) only one inflexion occurs at 0.75 mole of hydrazine per mole of ferricyanide in all conditions of alkalinity. Since the inflexion is affected by oxygen gas, the result is explained in terms of the equation :

TABLE 4—0.0937 M HYDRAZINE SOLUTION WAS ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00932 M FERRICYANIDE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Conc. of KOH Soln. (approx.)	Colour	Temp./period of storage	Moles of hydrazine per mole of ferricyanide
1.	1 N	Colourless	30°/7 days	0.75
2.	0.1 N	"	"	0.75
3.	Borate buffer (pH=9.018)	Light Yellow	"	0.75
4.	Aq. medium (pH≈5)	Bright green to blue	"	0.3, 0.7

TABLE 5—0.04481 M KIO₄ SOLUTION ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00986 M HYDRAZINE SULPHATE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Acid concentration (approx.)	Colour	Temp./period of storage	Points of inflex (ml.)	Moles of hydrazine per mole of periodate
1.	0.1 N	Colourless to yellow	25°/72 hrs.	1.1	2.0
2.	1 N	"	"	1.1	2.0
3.	2 N	"	"	1.1	2.0
4.	4 N	"	"	1.1	2.0
5.	6 N	"	"	1.1	2.0
6.	8 N	"	"	1.1	2.0

The inflexion at 0.3 and 0.7 mole in lower pH(5) are consistent with the following stoichiometries :

In the case of periodate, when N₂H₄ is added to it, (Table 6) 2.02 moles of the latter are consumed per mole of the former with N₂ as the sole product of oxidation.

TABLE 6—0.1972 M HYDRAZINE ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00488 M KIO₄ SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Acid concentration (approx.)	Colour	Temp./period of storage	Points of inflexion (ml.)	Moles of hydrazine per mole of periodate
1.	0.1 N	Yellow to Colourless	25°/24 hrs.	0.5	2.0205
2.	1 N	"	"	0.5	2.0205
3.	2 N	"	"	0.5	2.0205
4.	4 N	"	"	0.5	2.0205
5.	6 N	"	"	0.5	2.0205

The slight shift from the exact stoichiometry (2:1) is due to the interaction of iodine, formed as an intermediate, with the hydrazine. That the final product of reduction is iodide, not iodine, is supported by the fact that the solution remains colourless at the end.

In the reverse case (Table 5,) exactly 2.0 moles of hydrazine per mole of periodate are consumed but iodine is visibly formed in the reaction. This corresponds to the equation. $4 IO_4^- + 8 N_2 H_4 + 4 H^+ = 3/2 I_2 + 7.5 N_2 + NH_3 + 16 H_2 O + HI$ The ratio of N_2/NH_3 in the products shows that the oxidation proceeds through simultaneous mono- and di-deelectronations.

The behaviour of molybdate is somewhat more surprising. If it were to act as a di-deelectronator, the products of oxidation would be N_2 or $N_2 H_4$ or both. Instead of this, three inflexions at 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 moles of Mo (VI) per mole of hydrazine are observed, if the latter is taken in excess (Table 7.). This result is consistent with the following sequence :

TABLE 7—0.091 M SODIUM MOLYBDATE ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00931 M HYDRAZINE SULPHATE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Acid concn-entrainment H_2SO_4	Colour of the mixture	Temp./period of storage	Moles of molybdate per mole of hydrazine
1.	Neutral	Light yellow to green blue	35°/72 hr.	0.5, 0.75, 1.25
2.	0.1 N	"	90° for an hour	0.5, 0.75, 1.25
3.	1 N	Light amber to blue	"	0.5, 0.75, 1.25
4.	2 N	"	"	0.5, 1.0, 1.50
5.	3 N	"	"	0.5, 1.0, 1.50
6.	4 N	Bright amber	"	0.5, 1.0, 1.50

Under conditions of lower acidity when molybdate solution exhibits a different colour, possibly because of the changed nature of Mo (VI) ions, the inflexions occur somewhat earlier. This may be due to lower but indefinite reduction potential of the Mo (VI) species.

In the reverse case (Table 8) three inflexions in neutral, four in $N H_2 SO_4$ and five in higher concentrations of $H_2 SO_4$ are observed. This can be explained as follows :

In neutral medium :

In $1 N H_2 SO_4$:

In $>1 N H_2 SO_4$:

TABLE 8—0.0931 M HYDRAZINE SULPHATE ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.0091 M SODIUM MOLYBDATE SOLUTION.

Sl. No.	Acid concn-entrainment $N_2 SO_4$	Colour of the mixture	Temp. /period of storage	Moles of hydrazine per mole of molybdate
1.	Neutral	Light blue to dark blue	35°/72 hr.	1.0, 1.5, 2.0
2.	1 N	Light blue to amber	"	0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 2.5
3.	2 N	Light amber	"	0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5
4.	3 N	Bright amber	"	0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5

In these and other oxidations reported earlier, there hardly appears any relationship between the nature of reactions and the redox potentials of the systems involved. On the basis of the potential data¹⁷ Ce(IV) would be grouped with periodate and ferricyanide with Mo (VI). But the results are incomparable. Corresponding E^0 data for hydrazine, however, suggest quantitative oxidations (large equilibrium constants) with these oxidants. Kinetic and mechanistic factors, rather than thermodynamic, therefore, obviously predominate. A thorough comparison is, however, not possible because redox potential data for any of the intermediate hydronitrogens are not known.

From the nature of the reacting species pure electron transfer mechanisms are ruled out. They may be supposed to proceed through atom transfers preceded by acid-base coupling of the Lewis type (Duke's generalisation¹⁸). In acid solutions, protonated hydrazinium ions can act as reactive nucleophiles. The oxidising particles are also correspondingly modified to become reactive electrophiles. Electron transfers then occur indirectly through bond ruptures and subsequent atom transfers. Ce (IV) and Mo (VI) in aqueous acidic solutions are known to exist as hydrated ions. The deelectronations may then be conveniently presumed to occur through the formation of hydrogen bridge, similar to $Fe^{++} Fe^{+++}$ exchange¹⁹, and subsequent transfer of a hydrogen atom from hydrazine species, the oxidants thus acting as mono-deelectronators. In case of periodate, these ions are known to be protonated to give reactive IO_3^+ electrophiles,

The reaction between the two similarly charged ions can again be understood in terms of a similar hydrogen bridge mechanism.

In case of alkaline ferricyanide, the role of .OH free radicals is possible which may be formed by the homolysis of $H_2 O_2$. The .OH radical generates, in turn,

N_2H_3 . free radical and this may account for the various types of polyhydronitrogens encountered in these oxidations.

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